

Polarography of some Substituted Azo Derivatives

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Acidic solutions of *p*-hydroxyazobenzene¹, β -hydroxy-7-(1-naphthylazo)-5-quinoline-sulphonic acid², 3,5-dimethyl-4-(4'-sulphonamidobenzeneazo)pyrazole³, 3-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(*N*-4'-methoxyphenyl-*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazole⁴ and arylidene aroyl hydrazides⁵ all underwent four-electron cleavage of the N-N bond. Malik *et al.*⁵, however, reported two-electron irreversible waves for 1-thiocarbamyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-substituted-arylazopyrazoles in the pH-range 3.0-10.0. Saber *et al.*^{7,8} obtained two two-electron steps for *p*-hydroxy-*p*-bisazobenzene in neutral and aqueous alkaline solutions. The above results were sufficiently varied and conflicting to call for further investigation on the behaviour of substituted azo derivatives. The present investigation was therefore conducted on the following compounds: 3-(2'-tolyl)-4-(benzeneazo)-5-methylpyrazole (I), 1-carbamido-3-(2'-tolyl)-4-(benzeneazo)-5-methylpyrazole (II) and 1-carbamido-3-(2'-tolyl)-4-(1'-chlorobenzeneazo)-5-methylpyrazole (III).

Results and Discussion

DC polarograms (Fig. 1) exhibited one wave and dpp (Fig. 2) and ac (Fig. 3) polarograms only one peak with constant current from pH 4.0 to pH 11.0 for all the three compounds. Cpc data, given later, indicated a four-electron reduction for all of them. High dc wave slopes (ca 0.065 V) and the high slopes of $\log [(I_p/I)^{1/2} \pm (I_p - I)/I]^{1/2}$ vs E_{dc} plots for ac polarograms at pH 3.0 and pH 7.0, viz. 0.285 and 0.250 V respectively, in comparison with the theoretical slope of 29 mV for a four-electron process, indicated total irreversibility. Slopes of dc $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots were 0.073, 0.085 and 0.076 V per pH-unit upto pH 7.0 and 0.042, 0.051 and 0.018 V per pH unit above pH 7.0 for the respective three compounds. The ratio of the $E_{1/2}$ vs pH slopes to wave-slopes for their acidic solutions was therefore nearly unity.

Scheme 1

Fig. 1. DC polarograms of I-III (0.1 mmol dm⁻³) at 298 K

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Fig. 2. Differential pulse polarograms of I-III (0.1 mol dm⁻³) at 298 K, pH = 4.0.

Fig. 3. AC Polarograms of II (0.1 mmol dm⁻³) at 298 K.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of I-III (0.1 mmol dm⁻³) at 298 K.

CV voltammograms did not exhibit any anodic peak (Fig. 4) for any of the azo derivatives at pH's 6.0 and 7.0. The i_p vs $V^{1/2}$ plots were straight-lines passing through the origin and the current function $i_p/V^{1/2}$ was independent of scan-rate, indicating uncomplicated charge-transfer process. The αn_a value from dc data comes out to be 0.91 (= 0.059/0.065) and from CV data 1.14 ($E_p - E_{p/2} = 0.042 \text{ V} = 0.048/\alpha n_a \text{ V}$). However, from the ac equation⁹,

$$E_{dc \text{ peak}} = E_{1/2} - \frac{RT}{2\alpha n_a F} \ln 1.907 \sqrt{\omega t}$$

αn_a did not give constant values but varied from 1.0 to 0.33 for the frequency range 17-775 Hz.

Coulometry and product analysis : The coulometric analysis showed that the electro-reduction occurred with the consumption of four-electron per molecule at pH 6.0 for all the three compounds (Table 1). Constant potential electrolysis (pH 6.0) was carried out at -1.0 V on a 20 ml solution (1.0 mmol) for 4 h. The resulting solution was made slightly alkaline and the product was extracted with benzene. The ir spectra of the reduced products and the original compound were taken. The N-H stretching band can be seen in the reduced product as a strong band at 3 300-3 030 cm⁻¹ and the absence of N=N band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ suggests that the N-N bond was split giving two amino derivatives. Extraction of the reduced product with petroleum ether, followed by dye test of the extract with β -naphthol yielded positive test for aniline(*o*-chloroaniline). Ir spectra of the residue still exhibited N-H stretching band indicating that the other product was also an aromatic amine.

The high slopes of the dc waves and ac peaks indicated that these compounds were reduced in two overlapping two-electron steps preceded by protonation ($E_{1/2}$ vs pH slope/wave slope ≈ 1). In alkali, this prior protonation occurred by participation of the aqueous solvent medium. The following reduction scheme (Scheme 1) involving electron-pair shift is based on the observations that hydrazones involve four electrons in their reduction to two primary amines⁵, whereas azo derivatives without electron-donating groups involve only two electrons, yielding hydrazo compounds³.

TABLE 1 – CONSTANT POTENTIAL COULOMETRY OF THE
PYRAZOLES I–III (1.0×10^{-6} mol) AT 298 K

pH = 6.03 Applied potential : -1.20 V (SCE)			
i_d (μ A)	Q (C)	Q (mF)	n
Compound I :			
0.700	—	—	
0.365	0.194	2.00	
0.200	0.295	3.05	4.25
0.125	0.348	3.60	
0.060	0.379	3.92	
Compound II :			
0.455	—	—	
0.350	0.099	1.023	
0.250	0.190	1.967	
0.180	0.244	2.532	4.0
0.125	0.287	2.978	
0.085	0.291	3.010	
0.050	0.339	3.500	
Compound III :			
1.12	—	—	
0.85	0.093 0	0.964	
0.54	0.186 9	1.936	4.15
0.32	0.282 4	2.926	
0.19	0.324 0	3.350	
0.12	0.348 0	3.606	

Experimental

The test solutions contained 0.1 millimolar depolariser 0.05 M acetic acid or glycine buffers, 0.005% gelatin and 10% aqueous methanol. Polarograms ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) for deaerated solutions were recorded using a Bruker Universal E310 polarograph in conjunc-

tion with Hewlett-Packard 7040 X-Y recorder. Capillary used had characteristics, $m = 1.312 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t = 4.1 \text{ s}$ at 70 cm height of Hg reservoir and controlled drop-time of 2 s was used for recording the polarograms. The pH-values of buffer solutions were checked with an Elico LI-120 pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH-unit).

Studies were conducted using various techniques, viz. dc, dpp, ac, cv in addition to cpc and cpe. A digital coulometer (model 640, the Electrosynthesis Co., U.S.A.) was used for the cpc studies. For cpe a locally made 5V, 3A potentiostat-galvanostat was used and the extent of electrolysis was monitored from time to time by recording polarograms with a dme already fitted into the cell. Products of electrolysis were identified by ir spectra.

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